

Teaching Quality: Its Influence on Learning Experiences and Engagement of Learners

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this study was to examine how teaching quality affected the learning experiences and involvement of primary school children in Monkayo's East District. It assessed instructional methodologies, pedagogical ability, and teacher-student interaction to determine instructional quality. It also measured student involvement in cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor domains, as well as learning experiences such as classroom structure, instructional strategies, student-teacher relationships, and assessments. A descriptive, quantitative methodology was used to collect information from 50 students and 50 instructors using structured questionnaires. The findings revealed that the quality of instruction was typically considered good, with substantial agreement among both students and instructors on its efficacy. Furthermore, the psychomotor and emotional categories got very positive feedback in terms of student engagement and learning outcomes. However, Pearson correlation analysis did not reveal a significant relationship between teaching quality and student involvement. Furthermore, a substantial negative association was found between teaching quality and learning outcomes. This suggests that learners' learning experiences may not always align with their perception of the quality of teaching. These findings underscore the importance of aligning teaching approaches with students' emotional and personal learning needs, thereby facilitating the transition to more comprehensive and student-centered educational methodologies.

Keywords: education, teaching, quality

INTRODUCTION

The quality of teaching is a critical factor that significantly influences learners' engagement and learning experiences. Research indicates that effective teaching practices are linked to improved student outcomes, including higher engagement levels, increased motivation, and enhanced academic achievement (Delfino, 2019). Despite the recognized importance of teaching quality, many educational systems face challenges related to varying teaching standards, inadequate teacher training, and insufficient resources, leading to inconsistent learner experiences. This inconsistency creates a pressing need to investigate how teaching quality can be optimized to improve educational outcomes across diverse learning environments.

In the United States, a meta-analysis by Kim, Jörg, and Klassen (2019) showed that teacher effectiveness is one of the most significant influences on student learning outcomes. Similarly, the US Department of Education study has consistently shown that high-quality teaching correlates with improved student performance, particularly in underprivileged schools (Didion, 2019). These findings underscore the universal relevance of

teaching quality in shaping learners' academic journeys. In Lucban, Quezon Province, the Department of Education has recognized teaching quality as a key determinant of student success. Gepil's (2020) research illustrates that teachers' pedagogical skills and classroom management strategies significantly influence student engagement and academic achievement.

However, challenges such as inadequate teacher training, low salaries, and high student-to-teacher ratios persist, hampering efforts to improve teaching quality (Dayuha, 2024). Addressing these issues is crucial for fostering a conducive learning environment that enhances students' academic performance. Despite the extensive research on teaching quality, there are notable gaps in understanding its precise influence on learners' experiences and academic performance across different contexts. Many existing studies concentrate on generalized educational frameworks, often overlooking the intricate relationships between teaching quality and student outcomes at the micro-level. This study seeks to address these gaps by examining how teaching quality shapes learner experiences and academic success in Monkayo, Davao de Oro, ultimately contributing to more tailored policy and practice recommendations to improve educational effectiveness.

This study aimed to examine the influence of teaching quality on learners' learning experience. By analyzing the impact of instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence, the study seeks to uncover the relationship between teaching quality and student achievement. This research aimed to contribute to developing effective teaching strategies and interventions that can enhance the overall learning experience and academic outcomes for learners across various educational contexts.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Urie Bronfenbrenner's Bio-Ecological Theory, which explains human development as a dynamic process shaped by interactions between the individual and multiple layers of their environment. The theory comprises five interrelated systems: the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, 2005). These systems operate together over time to influence how individuals grow, learn, and adapt. In the context of this research, the microsystem represents the classroom environment where teaching quality—reflected in instructional methods, teacher-student relationships, and pedagogical competence—directly impacts learners' academic engagement and performance. Positive interactions within this system can enhance the academic and emotional support learners receive, contributing to a more holistic learning experience. At the exosystem level, the study considers external factors that indirectly influence students, such as school leadership, the availability of instructional materials, and policies from the Department of Education. Although learners may not be directly involved in these systems, they shape the conditions for teaching and learning. The macrosystem encompasses the community's broader cultural, economic, and social norms. Rural areas like Monkayo East District include challenges like limited access to educational resources and unique cultural practices, which must be acknowledged when evaluating teaching quality and student engagement. Lastly, the chronosystem refers to the role of time in individual development and shifts in educational practices. This study focuses on Grades 4 to 6, a critical stage in a learner's academic journey. Changes in policies, teacher practices, or student maturity levels are also considered, as they affect how students perceive and respond to teaching. Bronfenbrenner's theory provides a comprehensive lens for understanding how multiple environmental layers influence learning outcomes. It supports the study's aim to examine how the quality of teaching impacts learners' engagement and experiences, particularly in the rural and resource-limited setting of Monkayo East District.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to investigate the influence of teaching quality on learners' learning experiences and academic performance. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of teaching quality of elementary teachers in terms of:
Instructional methods;
Teacher-student interaction;
Pedagogical competence?
2. What is the level of student engagement of learners in terms of
cognitive engagement
affective engagement
psychomotor engagement?
3. What is the level of learning experience of learners in terms of
organization and structure

teaching and learning
students and teachers
assessments and other set works?

4. Is there a significant relationship between teaching quality and student engagement of learners?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teaching quality and the learning experience of learner.

Null Hypotheses

The null hypothesis is formulated at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no significant relationship between teaching quality and student engagement of learners

There is no significant relationship between teaching quality and the learning experience of learners.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This study examined the influence of teaching quality on learners' learning experiences using a quantitative descriptive research design. The research is confined to selected schools under Monkayo East District in Davao de Oro, specifically Tubo Tubo Elementary School, Muños Elementary School, Sugod Elementary School, Upper Ulip Elementary School, and Samuag Elementary School, including its extensions—Boay Elementary School and Samuag Integrated Elementary School. This geographical limitation restricts the generalizability of the findings to schools outside this area or other educational contexts. The participants of the study consisted of 50 teachers and 50 students from Grades 4, 5, and 6 in these schools. By focusing exclusively on elementary learners and educators, the study omits insights from secondary and tertiary education settings, narrowing the scope to primary education. The research investigated three specific aspects of teaching quality: instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence, and their impact on learners' academic performance and overall learning experience. Other potentially influential factors, such as parental involvement, socio-cultural dynamics, and resource availability, are outside the scope of this study. Similarly, variables like teacher training, school leadership, and classroom environment are not addressed.

Literature Review

This part of the quantitative research presented the compilation of articles, works of literature, and studies that would give details and relevant information about the highlight of this present study. Online resources and other articles taken from various sources, such as books, published and unpublished journals, manuals, and electronic references, were of boundless implication as the supplementary description that could support this research paper. The typical indicators in which the teaching quality levels are assessed include instructional practices and outcomes. Praetorius et al. (2018) state that good teaching is linked to educators with deep content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and the ability to engage students with their learning processes. This multi-dimensional view implies that not just the content, but also how well the teacher connects with the students and changes the teaching strategies to interact with the learners in class effectively. Moreover, according to the study by Pharis et al. (2019), the overall rating of teachers through peer review and student feedback helps gain informative insights into their teaching practices and improves school practices continuously. Furthermore, a difference in teaching quality can also strongly impact engaging and motivating the students. According to Francis and Babu (2019), research showed that supportive and challenging classroom environments that teachers use enhance student engagement. Their findings show that teaching quality is interrelated to strategies employed by educators to engage students actively and induce a sense of belonging. The classroom and the above strengths now make teachers incorporate active learning techniques combined with student choice opportunities to increase a student's intrinsic motivation. This focus on engagement emphasizes teacher education programs that train teachers in skills that enhance an interactive and engaging classroom environment, leading to better academic outcomes. Moreover, Adnot et al. (2017) emphasize that the relationship between teaching quality and student success also establishes that teachers should always be given continuous professional development to be equipped with the most effective instruction strategies possible. Diverse needs of students entail learning by various methods, which may significantly interfere with learning environments. For this reason, quality teaching should be considered a complex construct, including dimensions of instruction effectiveness, student interaction, and constant improvement. All these factors directly influence students' academic journey and the entire education process. As Fauth et al. (2019) brought out, teaching quality goes beyond instructional methods and includes aspects of emotional and social support. According to this argument, supportive teachers heavily influence students' emotional well-being and academic motivation. Educators can acknowledge the holistic nature of teaching quality and improve the needs of students toward improved academic outcomes. Similarly, Adeniran (2020) highlighted that teacher-student relationships are foundational for powerful learning. When the students receive emotional support, they will likely become more involved with the material and take more interest in their

education. In addition, social-emotional learning in teaching practices may develop an even more positive classroom environment. Enhancing the classroom culture through trust and respect while teaching incorporates emotional support, creating a more complete educational experience. Another critical dimension that would evaluate the extent of teaching effectiveness is the relationship between teaching quality and assessment practices. Fischer et al. (2018) establish that formative assessments are fundamental to providing feedback that informs teaching and learning. Their research further indicates that high-quality teaching is often characterized by several ongoing assessment strategies that allow the educator to know student strengths and areas for improvement. This approach not only improves the quality of teaching but also fosters a classroom environment that favors lifelong learning. Various means of assessment allow teachers to modify instruction in response to students and help ensure higher achievements. Aligning assessment practices with teaching quality is pivotal in developing an education environment that responds sensitively to students. Further exploration of the impact of teaching quality on the learners' experiences can be seen through Tokan and Imakulata's work in 2019, in which they argue that successful teachers teach both knowledge and critical thinking and problem-solving. Their study showed that using various strategies or tools of interactive teaching, like collaborative learning and inquiry-based instruction, students would be more likely to engage deeply with the material. This engagement is essential for meaningful learning, directly affecting students' academic outcomes. Teaching quality levels may also differ greatly from one educational context or population to another. According to the study by Colvard et al. (2018), variables such as available school resources, community support, and teacher collaboration affect teaching quality. From this study, it was noted that well-resourced schools tend to use innovative strategies for teaching and promote continuing professional development. In the study conducted by Hanushek et al. (2019), resource-constrained schools may be unable to deliver quality teaching, affecting student results. This is a very interesting point that reflects why there needs to be systemic changes to create equitable access to quality education for all students. By addressing the contextual factors that influence teaching quality, educational policymakers can work towards creating more equitable learning environments that support the professional growth of educators and enhance student achievement. Generally, to explore the association between teaching quality and academic performance, El Said and Mandl (2021) emphasize how a teacher's response is an imperative part of quality instruction. It gives the learner clear insight into their performance and encourages them to perform better. The evidence points to the need for quality teaching practice to create a good learning environment. In addition, there is evidence that teacher feedback mechanisms can matter in improving the academic outcomes of their students. The critical role of feedback within teaching quality requires educators to develop their ability to give informative and constructive guidance. Therefore, the knowledge of feedback dynamics will improve instructional practice and, consequently, student learning. A feedback culture in the classroom might lead educators to a more involved and motivated group of learners.

Instructional methods. Instructional approaches are fundamental elements of the teaching and learning process. According to Garner and Kaplan (2018), the most effective instruction acts as an intermediary that gets the student involved in the learning process so that they develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The authors state that utilization of multiple instructional techniques, including direct instruction, cooperative learning, and problem-based learning, can accommodate different learning styles and preferences. Additionally, Hofer et al. (2021), through their findings, support the view that variation in teaching strategies leads to better student results. Teachers use different teaching techniques to engage students positively and productively, leading to better performance in class. A diversification strategy ensures all students can exercise and interact with the material in ways that appeal to them, fostering an inclusive learning setting. Another influence has been the introduction of technology into instruction. With the advent of digital technology, the face of education has changed radically. According to Yurtseven Avci et al (2020), digital tools can significantly contribute to teaching effectiveness to extend interactive and personalized learning experiences. The authors argue that technology permits differentiated instruction that enables teachers to organize their approaches to cater to the various needs of their students. Moreover, technology would facilitate collaboration. For example, Pedro et al. (2018) note that when students work on projects together, it is possible regardless of their location. For instance, it may provide access to a wide range of resources, including interactive simulations and multimedia content for better understanding complex concepts. These new technological advancements can create dynamic learning environments with vibrant engagement that stir students toward success. Furthermore, studies reveal that student-centered teaching approaches, like inquiry-based learning, have greatly developed critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Serin. (2018) further states that inquiry-based learning inspires students to investigate real-world problems and collaborate. This learning style stimulates a personal investment in the learning process, as individuals become more energetic participants instead of inactive information recipients. Similarly, Yoder et al. (2019) state that inquiry-based learning greatly enhances students' engagement and fosters a deeper understanding

of concepts. Their study reveals that when students can be curious, conduct research, and present their findings, they develop essential skills that transcend the classroom. Therefore, implementing student-centered instruction is pertinent in learner preparation for challenges ahead and inspiring lifelong learning. Besides inquiry-based learning, there is also a need to use formative assessment strategies within instructional methods that promote student growth. Studies by Ferreira et al. (2020) note that formative assessments offer a range of feedback guiding teaching and learning. According to the authors, the key characteristic of quality teaching is ongoing assessment strategies where educators can recognize students' strengths and weaknesses. This responsiveness enhances students' understanding and develops the growth mindset, empowering learners to improve their performance. Furthermore, Andersson and Palm (2018) also mentioned in favour of this view, explaining that formative assessment helps to create a collaborative learning environment wherein students are actively involved with their learning process. Including formative assessment in instructional methods encourages a responsive educational environment to support learners' success. Culturally responsive teaching strategies have become integral parts of the best instruction. Muñiz (2019) emphasizes that culturally responsive pedagogy acknowledges and appreciates students' cultural background and puts them into the actual learning experience. This promotes higher student engagement, a sense of belonging, and validation in the classroom setting. Further, Cruz et al. (2019) note that when teachers use culturally connected resources and background information, students are more at ease and will most likely understand and be able to retain what is learned. Ladson-Billings' work demonstrates how teachers can promote a fair and inclusive learning environment, honoring and accepting the differences of students, by using culturally responsive instructional practices, thus facilitating better academic results for all. Besides emotional intelligence, culturally responsive teaching practice has emerged as an essential element that changes the teaching quality. Wu et al. (2019) posit that teachers who respect students' cultural backgrounds while using those in their teaching approaches will have higher engagement of students and their awareness of the teaching process. Culturally responsive teaching helps students find their identities in curricula, which may increase students' motivation levels and thus their academic performance in return. Gay's findings indicate that instructors better facilitate more inclusive learning environments when they respect cultural differences and incorporate this perspective into their instructional programs. This correspondence between teaching quality and cultural responsiveness benefits not just students from diverse backgrounds but also all students in the educational process. Thus, teachers must continue the reflection process and constantly change to support their varied learners appropriately. Understanding the dynamics of teaching quality also requires examination of its effects upon diverse student populations. Research by Praetorius et al. (2018) illustrates that teaching quality has different implications for students from various socio-economic backgrounds. The study draws particular attention to the fact that high-quality teaching is essential for disadvantaged students, who have fewer opportunities for further support outside the classroom. Moreover, Chen and Yang (2019) pointed out that quality improvement of teaching must be a must to meet the requirement for equity outcomes in learning outcomes. In this context, educators need to acknowledge the pertinent needs of disadvantaged group students and design their instruction to resonate with them. Specific support and intervention systems may also be necessary. Finally, the accomplishment of a culturally responsive teaching environment could empower all students and give them value in learning experiences. This means that quality teaching must be pursued and must, in turn, commit to equity and inclusion in the educational landscape. Regarding specific teaching strategies, Tamsah et al. (2021) assert that active learning is an important aspect of teaching quality. Their study reveals that active learning approaches that include group discussions and hands-on activities profoundly increase student engagement and knowledge retention. This confluence of teaching strategies and student learning experiences is, therefore, a fundamental way to understand how teaching quality directly affects academic performance. Moreover, active learning results in a deeper understanding of the subject, encouraging students to apply concepts to practical situations. This method promotes critical thinking and important collaboration skills that are vital for future success. The more engaged the student is in the learning process, the more they can show increased motivation and enthusiasm for their studies. The positive effects of active learning on teaching quality underpin the demand for educators to embrace innovative instructional methods in their practice. Quality teaching is one factor that influences the learning experience and learning outcomes for the learners. Kim and Seo (2018) state that appropriate instructional practices, such as explicit instructions or interactive strategies, enhance learners' understanding and memorability. The authors also show that if teachers offer their students an opportunity to adopt different learning styles, they can create a more inclusive class climate. Such flexibility also enhances student achievement. Still, it fosters a more well-rounded learning experience for the students, thus making the quality of teaching an indispensable component in educational research.

Teacher-student interaction. The interaction between teachers and students plays a significant role in student learning. It affects students' academic performance as well as their psychology. According to Cheng and Tsai

(2019), positive teacher-student interactions contribute to feelings of belongingness, making students want to learn more. As this study has also depicted, if the educators initiate supportive relationships, the students would be more active during classroom activities. For instance, according to Shih et al. (2018), research reveals that high-quality teacher-student interactions are associated with better academic results and higher student satisfaction. Thus, prioritizing strong interpersonal relationships will allow educators to cultivate a more conducive learning environment for cognitive and emotional development. The relationship between teaching quality and student motivation is critically examined by Burchinal (2018). According to their findings, effective teachers adopting motivational strategies such as goal setting and positive reinforcement can increase students' intrinsic motivation to learn. That means that motivation is also related to academic performance, so teaching quality is not only about content but also the presentation and reception of that content. According to Abuhassna et al. (2020), motivational strategies may foster a positive classroom environment; children would feel encouraged to take risks in learning. The authors propose an integrated approach where motivational techniques would be assumed in regular teaching activities. Teachers can encourage pupils to blossom by instilling a caring and encouraging environment. Through the exploration of motivation within the context of teaching quality, practical education is multifaceted, thus playing an important role in determining students' success. Moreover, effective teacher-student interaction involves clear communication and active listening. According to Pennings et al. (2018), teachers who actively listen to their students and respond thoughtfully are better equipped to address their needs and concerns. This type of engagement enhances the learning experience and builds trust and respect between teachers and students. In addition, Abbaset et al. (2020) point out that open lines of communication facilitate feedback, by which students can convey their thoughts and feelings about the learning process. Consequently, educators should adapt the instructional methods better to meet the needs and interests of the students; this would further increase the chances of personalized learning, thus improving students' academic performance. Furthermore, the role of feedback in teacher-student interactions cannot be overlooked. According to Harper (2018), timely and constructive feedback is essential for promoting student learning and self-regulation. Shute emphasizes that effective feedback informs students about their progress and guides them in understanding how to improve. Similarly, Miao et al. (2022) observe that when a teacher provides specific feedback, it enhances students' understanding of the subject and urges them to approach excellence. Thus, if the tools of feedback mechanisms are included in teacher-student interactions, this would be very important to foster student growth and encourage a culture of continuous learning. The impact of teaching quality on students' emotional intelligence has also garnered attention in recent years. According to Chen and Guo (2020), educators play a crucial role in fostering emotional intelligence among learners by modeling effective interpersonal skills and creating supportive classroom environments. Their research indicates that when teachers prioritize social-emotional learning, students are better equipped to manage their emotions and build positive relationships. It is important because emotional intelligence is correlated with academic success and overall well-being. Moreover, incorporating emotional intelligence in the curriculum makes the students more able to cope with difficulties and collaborate constructively with peers. Hence, teaching excellence must embrace intellectual development and a student's emotional and social development, which would integrate the holistic approach into education. Apart from academic support, there are teacher-student interactions. Such research studies, especially that of Kim et al. (2022), depict SEL as positive relationships between teachers and their students, promoting social-emotional learning competencies such as empathy and resilience. The authors postulate that when teachers exercise SEL skills in their interactions with the students, their adoption is more likely in their daily lives. This would create an encouraging class environment and better prepare the students for life's challenges. Under these conditions, teachers are likely to promote supportive relationships between themselves and students that stimulate academic and personal growth. Perception by the learner of teaching quality can help inform their experiences during academic practice. Tsay et al. (2018) noted that "student ratings of instructors have significant predictive validity when it comes to predicting engagement and perceived support in the classroom." For instance, the case study indicates that if the students are satisfied with the qualifications and friendliness of their teachers, then their performance is enhanced. This underlines the importance of teachers nurturing quality relationships with their students, thus establishing a favorable learning environment. Furthermore, the awareness of students' perceptions directs teachers to be more attentive to their pedagogical activities and people skills practices. A teacher can increase students' confidence and participation by facilitating an open and friendly classroom culture. This atmosphere helps improve the whole learning experience and fosters higher academic output. As students feel valued and understood, they are more likely to take ownership of their learning and strive for success. Furthermore, recognition has become rife that the teacher-student relationship is a critical factor towards improving education outcomes when viewed in line with cultural responsiveness. Through such teaching, as put by Cunningham (2019), this "culturally responsive teaching" values and recognizes the diversities presented in the backgrounds of learners, creating an even more inclusive learning environment. It results in teachers

connecting with learners personally, making the curriculum more relevant and accessible. Additionally, according to Warren (2018), for students to be more engaged with their studies and ultimately achieve greater success, educators must "immerse themselves in culturally responsive practices in their interactions with students." In other words, embracing diversity and making room for inclusive interaction enhances the educational experience for all students and contributes to equity in learning outcomes. Additionally, peer relationship significantly affects teaching quality and student learning. According to Maunder (2017), appropriate positive peer interactions help develop a supportive classroom environment where students are valued and engaged. The study reveals that with academic achievement, students who work and support each other increase their performance since they develop vital social competencies and feel a sense of belonging. Educators can leverage student-to-student relationships fostered through cooperative learning to enhance teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Furthermore, from the efforts of Ingraham et al. (2018), setting up a peer mentoring program may further contribute to success in school by enabling more active participants of the learning environment to contribute to their peers. This way, the importance of peer dynamics would be evident, and teachers would create a more inclusive, supportive environment for learning, culminating in improved academic performance for all students. The relationship between teaching quality and student motivation is critically examined by Burchinal (2018). According to their findings, effective teachers adopting motivational strategies such as goal setting and positive reinforcement can increase students' intrinsic motivation to learn. That means that motivation is also related to academic performance, so teaching quality is not only about content but also the presentation and reception of that content. According to Abuhassna et al. (2020), motivational strategies may foster a positive classroom environment; children would feel encouraged to take risks in learning. The authors propose an integrated approach where motivational techniques would be assumed in regular teaching activities. Teachers can encourage pupils to blossom by instilling a caring and encouraging environment. Through the exploration of motivation within the context of teaching quality, effective education is shown to be multifaceted, thus playing an important role in determining students' success.

Pedagogical competence. Pedagogical competence is one of the key aspects of effective teaching, comprising knowledge, skills, and attitudes that will enable a teacher to teach successfully. For example, Murkatik et al. (2020) refer to three critical components of pedagogical competence: content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and pedagogical knowledge. Content knowledge is the understanding of the material one intends to teach. In contrast, pedagogical content knowledge is the way that knowledge will be conveyed in a manner that makes it accessible to students. In addition, pedagogical knowledge includes several strategies and techniques teachers can use to reach students. With this all-inclusive perception of pedagogical competence, there comes an added importance for greater educational achievement and a more supportive learning environment. Besides the content mastery, the pedagogical competence requires understanding the diverse needs of students. In this respect, studies by Aimah and Ifadah (2023) stated that a teacher should be aware of and accommodate individual differences in learners regarding their styles, interests, and backgrounds. Consequently, it enables the realization of an all-inclusive classroom in which every student will feel respected and supported. Additionally, Susanto et al. (2020) suggest that teachers must employ various instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. Educators can improve engagement and academic performance by adapting their teaching approaches to accommodate different learning preferences, ultimately fostering a more equitable educational experience. Another area is classroom management, which is a firmly integrated part of pedagogical competence. Effective classroom management contributes to the quality of learning and student success, as Franklin and Harrington (2019) reported. The authors state that teachers must set clear expectations, routines, and consequences to establish a structured but supportive learning environment. In addition, according to Berger et al. (2018), classroom management practices should aim at creating positive interactions between students and teachers. A friendly classroom atmosphere encourages better-performing and attending students, leading to more positivity in the learning environment. Another important pedagogical competence includes making practical assessments and evaluations of student learning. As Rusilowati and Wahyudi point out, "formative assessment is one practice critical to the support of student growth and in guiding instructional decisions" (2020). The authors provide the argument that continuous assessments are helpful to track the progress of students, fill the gaps in learning, and modify teaching accordingly. Further, Gage (2018) supports this concept as he maintains that feedback acquired from assessment activities is critical in raising students' attainment. With practical assessment as part of their pedagogy, instructors can make the learning atmosphere responsive, allowing students to improve with greater success continually. Moreover, Hayat et al. (2020) mentioned that teacher professional development significantly impacts the quality of teaching. They stated that ongoing professional development enables teachers with new pedagogical approaches and theories they can deliver into the classroom in a way that can directly inform their practice. Implications of the study suggested that teachers who have more involvement in training and

development initiatives exhibit increased best practices in instruction that subsequently yield better engagement and improved performance among students. This underlines the need for institutions of learning to offer continuous professional development to enhance the quality of teaching. Moreover, peer collaboration and mentorship associated with professional development allow educators to attain a culture of shared learning and support about teaching. For example, Iglesias-Pradas et al. (2021) reported that investing in staff training is something that schools can use their resources to invest in to build a workforce better prepared to respond to their students' needs. Finally, the relationship between professional development and quality teaching suggests a need for improvement in practice. In addition, the interplay between teaching quality and academic performance extends to assessment practices. According to Hanushek et al. (2020), high-quality assessments aligned with learning objectives can provide valuable insights into student understanding. Their study underscores that formative assessments, which emphasize ongoing feedback and adjustment of teaching methods, are crucial for supporting learners' academic journeys. This relationship between assessment quality and teaching efficacy, as discussed in research done by Gess-Newsome et al. (2017) also deepens the multifacetedness of teaching quality and has a crucial role to play in student outcomes. Effective assessment practices can also be used to guide instructional planning and to identify deficits. Assessments as learning tools can help educators create a more responsive and dynamic teaching environment. Improvement in teaching effectiveness, and consequently in student success, requires enhanced refinement of assessment practices in continuous development. This forms one of the strongest supports for the argument that teaching quality is not just about what is taught but also how student learning is assessed and supported. Professional development is essential to the enhancement of pedagogical competency. According to Fernández-Batanero et al. (2020), continuous learning is a requirement among instructors, as it allows them to stay abreast of existing best practices and emerging trends in education. The authors posit that participation in professional development, including workshops or engaging with collaborative learning communities, can significantly boost teachers' pedagogical skills and knowledge. However, Sancar et al. (2021) emphasize that reflective practice is essential for instructors to evaluate their success and understand their strengths and weaknesses. Thus, the commitment to continuous professional development can enable teachers to refine their pedagogical competence and gain better learning experiences with their students.

Student Engagement. Student engagement has been a crucial factor in determining academic success, with numerous studies highlighting its influence on students' learning experiences. According to Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2010), engagement is conceptualized in three dimensions: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive. Behavioral engagement refers to students' participation in academic and social activities, while emotional engagement pertains to students' attitudes toward learning, school, and teachers. Cognitive engagement, on the other hand, reflects students' effort to comprehend complex ideas. These dimensions are vital because they are directly correlated with academic outcomes and students' overall learning experience (Kahu, 2013). The lack of student engagement in these areas can result in poor academic performance and diminished classroom experiences. Several factors contribute to disengagement in students, including uninspiring teaching methods and a lack of student-centered pedagogies. Sahlberg (2011) emphasized that traditional, teacher-centered approaches often fail to ignite student interest and participation. Similarly, Zyngier (2012) found that student disengagement occurs when lessons are irrelevant to students' interests or disconnected from real-world applications. This disengagement, in turn, leads to reduced motivation, which further impairs students' academic performance and participation in learning activities. These findings suggest the need for innovative, student-centered approaches that encourage active involvement to enhance learning experiences and engagement. Technology integration is another critical factor that impacts student engagement. According to Chen, Lambert, and Guidry (2010), students are more engaged in learning environments incorporating digital tools and resources. With the rise of online learning platforms, digital engagement strategies, such as interactive activities and multimedia resources, have increased cognitive and emotional involvement in learning. Similarly, Davies, Dean, and Ball (2013) argued that using technology facilitates personalized learning experiences that cater to students' diverse needs and learning styles, thus increasing their engagement and motivation to learn. However, it is essential to ensure that these technological tools are used effectively and in a manner that promotes deep learning rather than superficial engagement. A supportive classroom environment also plays a pivotal role in fostering student engagement. Research conducted by Reeve and Tseng (2011) shows that autonomy-supportive teaching practices, where students are given choices and a sense of ownership in their learning, significantly increase their engagement levels. In line with this, Skinner, Furrer, Marchand, and Kindermann (2008) found that teacher-student relationships built on trust and mutual respect create a positive learning environment where students feel more inclined to participate actively. Such findings highlight the importance of teacher behavior in shaping a conducive atmosphere that enhances engagement and, consequently, learning experiences. Lastly, the role of formative assessment in improving student engagement cannot be overstated. According to Nicol and

Macfarlane-Dick (2006), providing timely and constructive feedback helps students understand their learning progress and identify areas that require improvement, promoting greater engagement. Similarly, Black and Wiliam (2010) argue that formative assessment encourages self-regulation and a growth mindset, enabling students to participate in their learning journey actively. When students receive regular feedback, they are likelier to take ownership of their learning process, engage more deeply with the material, and experience more significant academic gains.

Cognitive. Cognitive engagement refers to a student's intellectual investment in their learning process. According to Fredricks et al. (2019), cognitive engagement is a critical predictor of academic success, as it involves deeper learning, critical thinking, and the application of knowledge. Studies have shown that cognitively engaged students are more likely to retain and apply information beyond the classroom. A study by Pedler et.al (2020) found that cognitive engagement is strongly influenced by teaching quality. Teachers who incorporate active learning strategies, such as problem-solving activities and inquiry-based learning, increase students' cognitive engagement. These methods stimulate students' higher-order thinking and foster critical thinking skills. Furthermore, an essential factor in cognitive engagement is the use of metacognitive strategies. Research by Elbyaly and Elfeky (2022) shows that when students are taught how to monitor and regulate their thinking processes, they become more cognitively engaged. Teachers who model metacognitive strategies help students understand the material more deeply, leading to enhanced learning outcomes. Moreover, Li et.al (2024) found that interactive technologies can significantly boost cognitive engagement. Digital platforms that encourage collaboration, such as virtual discussion boards or interactive simulations, enable students to engage with content actively and deepen their understanding of complex topics. According to Sun et.al (2023), self-directed learning is a key component of cognitive engagement. When students are allowed to take responsibility for their learning, they are more likely to engage in critical thinking and explore topics in greater depth. This autonomy promotes a sense of ownership over their learning, enhancing both motivation and achievement. In addition, cognitive engagement also involves task value, which refers to how much students find a task meaningful and relevant. A study by Vo (2023) suggests that students who perceive learning tasks as valuable invest more cognitive effort in completing them. Teachers who connect course content to real-world applications or students' interests tend to increase cognitive engagement. Specifically, feedback plays an essential role in cognitive engagement. According to Jin (2024), timely and constructive feedback helps students gauge their understanding and areas for improvement. This feedback loop encourages students to process information actively, reinforcing their cognitive engagement with the subject matter.

Affective. Affective engagement refers to students' emotional investment in the learning process. It includes feelings of interest, enjoyment, and a positive attitude toward learning (Jang et al., 2020). According to Skinner and Pitzer (2019), affective engagement is vital for student motivation and persistence in learning—positive emotions related to learning lead to increased effort and academic achievement. The role of teacher-student relationships in fostering affective engagement cannot be understated. Research by Poulou and Garner (2024) indicates that students with positive relationships with their teachers are more emotionally engaged in their learning. Teachers who show empathy, encouragement, and emotional support foster a safe environment where students feel comfortable participating and taking risks. Apart from that, classroom climate is also critical for affective engagement. Research by Hettinger et.al (2024) found that a favorable, supportive classroom climate leads to greater student emotional involvement. Teachers who create a welcoming atmosphere and encourage collaborative learning help students feel valued, which leads to higher levels of affective engagement. Also, affective engagement can be influenced by the relevance of the content. According to Schreiner et.al (2021), when students find the material emotionally resonant or aligned with their interests, they engage more deeply with the content. Teachers who incorporate real-world connections and personal relevance into lessons foster greater emotional investment from their students. Furthermore, intrinsic motivation plays a significant role in affective engagement. Kanellopoulou and Giannakoulopoulos, (2020) argue that intrinsically motivated students are more likely to develop a love for learning and remain emotionally engaged in the classroom. Teaching strategies that foster curiosity, exploration, and a sense of purpose are vital for promoting intrinsic motivation. Finally, student well-being influences affective engagement. A study by Hilliard et al. (2020) found that students who experience lower stress and anxiety levels are more likely to be emotionally engaged in their learning. Teachers who create a supportive, understanding environment contribute to the overall emotional well-being of their students, thereby enhancing affective engagement.

Psychomotor. Psychomotor engagement refers to the physical involvement of students in the learning process, including their participation in hands-on activities, movement, and manipulation of materials (Thiri et.al, 2024). Research has shown that incorporating physical activity into lessons enhances engagement and memory retention. In a study by Shobr et al. (2024), it was found that active learning strategies that involve physical movement—such as group activities, role-playing, and hands-on experiments—are particularly effective in promoting psychomotor engagement. These activities engage students physically and encourage collaboration and teamwork, fostering a dynamic learning environment. According to Arman et.al (2024), kinesthetic learning is closely linked to psychomotor engagement. Students physically engaged in tasks are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of the content. Teachers incorporating kinesthetic activities into their lessons cater to diverse learning styles, helping students develop cognitive and physical skills. Moreover, the importance of movement-based learning for younger students has been highlighted by Aloizou et.al (2024). Their study found that incorporating physical movement—such as games or tasks that require hand-eye coordination—into lessons significantly boosts engagement, especially among primary school students. This type of engagement supports physical development and increases overall enthusiasm for learning.

Learning Experience. Academic performance of the learners is a crucial indicator that evaluates the success and effectiveness of education. This usually involves an assessment of students' academic performances through grades, results obtained from standardized tests, and various appraisals to show the level at which a student has grasped the curriculum. Ariastuti and Wahyudin (2022) assert that various factors drive students' academic performance, including socio-economic status, resource availability, and quality of instruction received. The report clearly states that learning outcome inequalities arise from unequal opportunities that significantly affect students' overall outcomes during education. Teachers and policymakers must understand such factors to evolve suitable interventions that can improve learning outcomes among diverse populations of students. However, motivation also plays a significant role in academic performance. According to Theobald (2021), the intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors highly enhance the involvement of a learner and the results they achieve. The primary source of intrinsic motivation is a student's interest in the subject they are studying, likely leading to deeper learning and higher achievement. Conversely, extrinsic motivation, which can improve performance but may not foster a long-term love for learning, can be manifested by extrinsic rewards. Additionally, Lu et al. (2018) posit that increasing learner autonomy and competence fosters intrinsic motivation, promoting better learner academic outcomes. As such, the motive is essential for instructors to foster better learner academic performance and the learning experience. Additionally, teacher quality's effects on students' academic performance are extensively documented. According to Burić and Kim (2020), effective teachers have strong subject matter knowledge and use a variety of instructional approaches that capture student attention while promoting learning. The author states that several studies have verified that teacher effectiveness is always associated with student achievement. Egalite and Kisida (2017) further argue that high-quality teaching practices, which include formative assessment and differentiated instruction, account for much improvement in learners' academic performance. Investing in teacher training and professional development significantly enhances the quality of teaching and, subsequently, the students' educational outcomes. The influence of a supportive learning environment also plays a crucial role in academic performance. According to Namoun and Alshantqiti (2020), students who perceive their school climate as positive are more likely to exhibit higher levels of academic achievement. The authors emphasize the importance of creating a safe and supportive atmosphere that fosters collaboration, respect, and belonging among students. In addition, research by Pacaol (2021) indicates that favorable school climate is well associated with students' emotional welfare and thus their motivation to learn and thereby improve learners' academic performance by focusing on developing an inclusive learning environment.

Besides intrinsic motivation and instruction quality, the effect of peer relationships in shaping academic outcomes has been viewed as something of interest. Roksa and Kinsley (2018) assert that positive peer interactions that offer social support influence student success at school. The author indicates that students with strong social connections tend to engage in collaborative learning that may improve understanding and retention of course material. In addition, the work of Agustina et al. (2021) also indicates that cooperative learning strategies, whereby there is teamwork among students working together towards a common goal, facilitate a sense of community and enhance higher academic achievement. Educators can create a collaborative learning environment, improving academic performance of students, and developing their educational experience by providing positive peer relationships, cooperative learning approaches, etc. Another critical aspect of learning that determines the outcome is self-regulation. Learners should be able to manage their learning processes through setting goals, monitoring progress, and adjusting strategies as necessary. According to Edossa et al. (2017), those students with good self-regulation skills tend to have better academic performance due to effective organization of learning

efforts. These students are more likely to demonstrate self-motivated learning behaviors such as seeking help when necessary and utilizing feedback for improvement. Asikainen et al. (2017) posit that teaching students how to use self-regulatory techniques may bolster academic success and, at the same time, enhance the students' autonomy in their educational success for an extended period. Educators can empower learners with skills that promote continued academic performance by encouraging self-regulation. In addition, integrating technology in learning has increasingly contributed to learners' academic performance. Lee, van Lai, and Bower (2019) highlighted that including digital tools, such as educational apps, online resources, and interactive platforms through technology, is excellent for raising students' engagement and increasing learning outcomes. The authors point out that technology permits personalization in learning, with students learning at their own pace using relevant resources. Along this line, Dinc (2019) agrees with the perception that technology can enhance collaboration, obtain real-time feedback, and use different forms of content delivery that are likely to improve performance in academic exercises. As technology evolves, educators must leverage these tools to create dynamic and effective learning environments that support student achievement. Lastly, school leadership and administrative support significantly affect student learning results. According to Leithwood et al. (2019), "effective school leaders provide a positive learning climate through clear goals, adequate resources and support provided for teachers, and a pervasive culture of high expectations." These authors argue that superior instruction is maximized if the school administrators foster collaborative relations among the teachers and support them actively. Simultaneously, Torres (2019) concluded that school leadership favoring teacher's professional development and collaboration leads to better instructional practices and encourages students' academic achievements. With strong leadership and a supportive school culture, educational institutions set the conditions students need to excel academically.

Organization and Structure. Research on the role of organization and structure in the learning experience has emphasized the need for well-organized curricula to ensure effective student engagement. According to Meth, Thomson, and Brough (2019), clear and coherent course structures directly impact student success, as they provide a roadmap that guides learners through progressively challenging content. A structured curriculum allows students to learn systematically, effectively ensuring foundational knowledge is built upon. Another significant factor is how teachers scaffold content to align with the students' cognitive load. Foster (2023) highlights that the structure of lessons—organized into manageable chunks—facilitates learning by reducing cognitive overload. This technique is instrumental in complex subjects where knowledge needs to be broken down into digestible units for better retention. Research by Marcos et al. (2020) demonstrates that a structured learning environment fosters higher levels of student achievement. In their study, students taught in a well-organized, clear framework displayed better retention and problem-solving skills. This suggests that a coherent structure is essential for maximizing learning outcomes. In addition, according to Cayubit (2022), a well-organized structure enhances student motivation, as learners know what is expected and can visualize their academic progress. This visual understanding contributes to a sense of achievement and improves engagement with the learning materials. The clarity of the learning structure also helps students set realistic goals. Also, effective use of technology contributes to the organization and structure of lessons. A study by Haleem (2022) found that digital tools that organize course materials and track student progress significantly improve the learning experience. Structured online platforms create clear pathways for students, allowing easy access to learning resources, assignments, and feedback. Furthermore, Ojong (2023) suggests that a clear organizational structure is especially beneficial for diverse classrooms. By offering differentiated pathways within a well-structured curriculum, teachers can meet the varied needs of students, thus ensuring that each student's learning experience is maximized according to their progress.

Teaching & Learning. The interaction between teaching practices and learning outcomes is central to the learning experience. As Morris, Perry, & Wardle (2021) highlighted, effective teaching strategies such as formative assessments, collaborative learning, and feedback are critical to fostering deep learning experiences. These strategies encourage students to take ownership of their learning, facilitating cognitive and affective engagement. A study by Gholam (2019) found that inquiry-based teaching methods involving active student participation result in more profound and enduring learning outcomes. Such teaching approaches challenge students to think critically and develop problem-solving skills, creating a richer learning environment. Research by Decristan et al. (2019) showed that teaching quality impacts how well students retain information. Teachers who use various teaching methods, including direct instruction, group discussions, and hands-on activities, create an environment where students actively engage with content and learn more effectively. This multidimensional approach fosters a dynamic classroom experience. Moreover, the importance of student-teacher interactions in the teaching and learning process is well-documented. According to Martin and Collie (2019), a positive relationship between

teachers and students enhances learning experiences. Teachers who actively engage with students, offer encouragement, and provide constructive feedback contribute to improved student confidence and motivation. Beyond that, an aspect of teaching that has gained attention is using adaptive learning technologies, which cater to individual learning needs. A study by Taylor et.al (2021) found that personalized learning experiences, facilitated by adaptive learning technologies, allow students to work at their own pace while still receiving the necessary support to succeed. Additionally, Cruz et.al (2020) argue that culturally responsive teaching strategies significantly improve the teaching and learning experience. Teachers who incorporate culturally relevant materials and acknowledge students' diverse backgrounds create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. This approach fosters a deeper connection to the subject matter.

Students & Teachers. The relationship between students and teachers has long been recognized as a critical factor in the learning experience. In their study, Reeve, Cheon, and Jang (2019) found that the quality of teacher-student interactions influences student motivation and academic achievement. A positive relationship fosters an environment where students feel valued, leading to increased engagement and better learning outcomes. A study by Zhao and Chang (2019) found that students' perceptions of teacher support and fairness are key predictors of their learning experience. When students perceive their teachers as supportive and fair, they are more likely to engage actively in class, participate in discussions, and complete assignments. In addition, the impact of teacher feedback on the student-teacher relationship has also been explored. Amerstorfer and Freiin von Münster-Kistner (2021) found that feedback, when delivered appropriately, strengthens the bond between students and teachers. Effective feedback is both evaluative and formative, offering guidance on improving performance, which can positively influence student attitudes and motivation. Furthermore, teacher presence in the classroom is central to students' emotional and academic experience. According to Tackie (2022), when teachers maintain a strong physical and emotional presence in class, students feel more secure and are more likely to engage with the lesson. Teacher presence fosters community and belonging in the classroom, essential components for a positive learning experience. A study by Tran (2019) demonstrated that student outcomes improve when teachers and students share a collaborative approach to learning. Teacher collaboration with students through joint problem-solving and shared decision-making in classroom activities helps establish a supportive, dynamic environment that promotes active participation. Besides this, the emotional well-being of students has been shown to influence their relationship with teachers significantly. Granziera et.al (2022) highlight that students who feel emotionally supported by their teachers are more likely to perform well academically. This emotional support is a key component of effective teaching, promoting a learning environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves. Lastly, recent research by Makoelle (2019) has emphasized the importance of teacher empathy. Teachers who demonstrate empathy towards their students build trust and a sense of safety, which enhances students' learning experiences. Empathy allows teachers to address students' needs, creating a more personalized and supportive learning environment.

Assessment and Other Set Works. The role of assessment in shaping students' learning experiences is well-documented. According to Maki (2023), assessments are tools for measuring learning and key components of the learning process. Formative assessments, in particular, provide continuous feedback that helps students identify areas for improvement and adjust their learning strategies accordingly. Research by Moss and Brookhart (2019) suggests that assessments should be aligned with learning objectives to reflect student progress accurately. Well-designed assessments provide a structured learning environment where students understand their learning goals and expectations. A study by Pitt, Bearman, and Esterhazy (2020) found that regular, low-stakes assessments increase student engagement by providing immediate feedback and fostering a growth mindset. Students who regularly receive constructive feedback are more likely to see learning as an ongoing process, leading to continuous improvement. Moreover, using peer assessments in the classroom has also benefited learning experiences. According to Meijer et al. (2020), peer assessments encourage students to engage critically with each other's work, fostering collaborative learning. This type of assessment not only improves academic performance but also enhances students' communication and critical thinking skills. A study by Kelley et.al (2019) emphasized the importance of formative assessment in student-centered classrooms. The findings indicate that when assessments are integrated into the learning process—rather than serving as an afterthought—they significantly enhance students' ability to apply knowledge and improve performance. In addition, a Gallardo (2022) study revealed that well-structured summative assessments, when clearly aligned with course objectives, not only provide students with a sense of closure but also create opportunities for self-reflection on their academic journey. This alignment fosters a deeper understanding of the learning outcomes and reinforces the connection between the assessment and the skills or knowledge gained. Moreover, such assessments contribute to a more fulfilling and meaningful learning experience by allowing students to recognize their progress, identify

areas for improvement, and celebrate their achievements. Finally, a recent meta-analysis by Dudley (2023) concludes that a combination of formative, summative, and peer assessment provides the most effective feedback for students. When teachers use a variety of assessments, students receive a well-rounded perspective on their academic progress, helping them engage more deeply with their learning process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Locale

This study was conducted in selected public elementary schools under the Monkayo East District's jurisdiction in Davao de Oro, Philippines. The participating schools include Tubo Tubo Elementary School, Muños Elementary School, Sugod Elementary School, Ulip Elementary School, and Samuag Elementary School, along with their extensions — Boay Elementary School and Samuag Integrated Elementary School. Monkayo is a first-class municipality and one of the most progressive towns in Davao de Oro.

Design

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. A quantitative approach was used, as the research aimed to quantify the influence of teaching quality on learners' learning experiences in selected schools under the Monkayo East District in Davao de Oro, Philippines. (Creswell, 2012). This approach is appropriate because it enables the researcher to define and measure variables such as instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence, allowing for the identification of patterns and trends within the elementary school setting. Creswell (2012) emphasizes that a quantitative approach is best suited when the objective is to explain phenomena by identifying general tendencies and variations among responses. The correlational method was employed, given the study's objective of examining the relationship between teaching quality (instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence). The study investigated the correlation between these key aspects of teaching quality and learners' academic performance through correlation coefficients. As Creswell (2012) suggests, correlational research describes and measures the degree of association between two or more variables. This design allowed the researcher to determine whether significant relationships exist between the identified aspects of teaching quality of elementary learners in Samuag Elementary School.

Respondents

The participants of this study included 50 elementary school teachers and 50 pupils from Grades 4, 5, and 6 in selected schools under the Monkayo East District, Davao de Oro. These schools include Tubo Tubo Elementary School, Muños Elementary School, Sugod Elementary School, Upper Ulip Elementary School, and Samuag Elementary School, along with their extensions—Boay Elementary School and Samuag Integrated Elementary School. The teachers were selected through stratified random sampling to ensure a balanced representation across grade levels and varied teaching experiences. This approach includes diverse perspectives on instructional methods, teacher-student interactions, and pedagogical competence, enabling a comprehensive analysis of teaching quality. In addition to the teachers, 50 pupils from Grades 4, 5, and 6 across the selected schools also served as respondents. Their participation allowed the study to assess student engagement in three key domains: Affective Engagement – Emotional involvement and attitudes toward learning. Cognitive Engagement – Intellectual efforts and comprehension of learning materials. Psychomotor engagement– Physical participation and the application of learned skills in hands-on activities. The inclusion of students from these grade levels ensures a robust understanding of how teaching quality influences learners' experiences during a critical stage of their educational journey. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents—teachers and pupils- to uphold ethical standards. For students, consent from their parents or guardians was also secured. Only those who provided consent participated in the study. This ethical procedure guarantees that participation is voluntary and that the rights and welfare of respondents are protected. The diverse respondent pool allows for an in-depth exploration of the dynamics between instructional practices and student engagement in rural education.

Research Instrument

This survey questionnaire is designed to investigate the influence of teaching quality on learners' learning experiences and student engagement, drawing on the frameworks established by Shelley Hart and Shane Jimerson. It is divided into two parts, each addressing different aspects of the study. Part 1 evaluates the teaching quality regarding instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence. Respondents rated various statements to assess how effective teaching strategies and teacher behavior contribute to the learning environment. Part 2 focuses on the students' learning experiences, exploring their engagement through cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions. This section gauges the students' level of interest, emotional involvement,

and participation in academic activities, providing a comprehensive view of how teaching quality affects student engagement. Together, these parts form a cohesive tool that explores the relationship between teaching practices and student engagement, aligning with the engagement concepts outlined by Hart and Jimerson. Adapted from Economic and Social Research Council (2024), part 3 is on learning experiences, highlighting the following indicators: organization and structure, teaching and learning, students and teachers, and assessments and other set works.

Scale on the Level of Teaching Quality

Range	Description	Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Teaching quality is perceived as excellent, showcasing highly effective instructional methods and strong teacher-student interactions.
2.50- 3.49	Agree	Teaching quality is seen as good, demonstrating effective practices and positive interactions within the classroom.
1.50 -2.49	Disagree	Teaching quality is viewed as needing improvement, indicating some gaps in methods and interactions.
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Teaching quality is perceived as ineffective, highlighting substantial issues that require urgent attention.

Scale on the Level of Student Engagement

Range	Description	Interpretation
3.50 -4.00	Strongly Agree	Students demonstrate high levels of engagement, showing strong motivation and active participation in their learning.
2.50- 3.49	Agree	Students exhibit good engagement, participating well but occasionally needing encouragement to fully immerse themselves.
1.50 -2.49	Disagree	Student engagement is viewed as lacking, indicating some interest but with clear areas needing enhancement.
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Student engagement is perceived as very low, indicating a need for substantial improvement to foster greater motivation.

Scale on the Level of Learning Experience

Range	Description	Interpretation
3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	The learning experience is regarded as excellent, characterized by outstanding organization and effective teaching methods.
2.50- 3.49	Agree	The learning experience is seen as good, with solid organization and teaching but some areas that could be enhanced.
1.50 -2.49	Disagree	The learning experience is perceived as needing improvement, indicating a good foundation but with significant room for growth.
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	The learning experience is viewed as inadequate, showing noticeable gaps that need addressing for improvement.

Validation of Research Instrument

To ensure validity and reliability, the research instrument underwent a thorough review by a panel of education and research experts specializing in educational leadership. A pilot test was conducted with 20 teachers and school heads from a non-participating school to identify any issues related to the questions' clarity, relevance, or structure. Feedback from the pilot test will guide necessary revisions to enhance the instrument's effectiveness. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with a target coefficient of 0.70 or higher to ensure internal consistency across the various scales.

Data Collection Procedure

After receiving ethics approval, formal letters were submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro and the school head of Samuag Elementary School to request permission to conduct the research within the school. Obtaining Ethics Review Approval. Before the commencement of the research, the study proposal was submitted to an ethics review board to ensure that all ethical guidelines and standards are followed, particularly regarding the rights and welfare of the participants. Once permission was granted, informed consent forms were distributed to the elementary school teachers participating in the study. These forms outlined the purpose of the study, its procedures, potential risks and benefits, and the rights of the participants. Only those teachers who voluntarily provide signed consent will participate in the research. The research instrument was

validated to ensure its reliability and suitability for the respondents. The questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts in teaching quality and research methodology, followed by a pilot test with a small group of teachers from a non-participating school. Necessary revisions were made based on the feedback to ensure clarity and precision. Once permissions and consents were obtained, the questionnaires were distributed to the participants during working hours. The researcher will oversee the process, ensuring clear instructions are provided and that teachers complete the questionnaires accurately. After data collection, the responses were encoded into a secure database for analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software to examine the relationship between teaching quality (instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence) and learners' academic performance. The data collected in this study were analyzed using suitable statistical methods to examine the relationship between teaching quality and learners' academic performance. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution, were used to summarize the levels of instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence reported by the teachers at Samuag Elementary School. These tools will help identify trends and patterns in the data. To investigate the relationship between variables, Pearson's correlation was employed to measure the strength and direction of the association between teaching quality. Additionally, multiple regression analysis was performed to identify which aspects of teaching quality significantly influence learners' academic performance. A professional statistician reviewed and confirmed the appropriateness of these statistical methods for the study's objectives and data structure. All analyses were conducted using SPSS software to ensure precision and accuracy in the results.

Ethical Considerations

Before conducting the study on teaching quality and its influence on learners' academic performance at Samuag Elementary School, Salvacion, Monkayo, Davao de Oro, the researcher will take necessary steps to ensure the ethical protection of all participants. This study aimed to provide valuable insights into how instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence affect the academic performance of elementary learners. The findings informed educational practices and supported improved teaching quality at the elementary level. Results were shared with educational stakeholders to enhance learner outcomes in similar settings. All participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, scope, and procedures. They voluntarily provided consent after understanding their role in the research. It was also emphasized that participants have the right to withdraw from the study without any repercussions. The study poses minimal risks to participants. All data collection occurred in a safe and respectful environment. Participants were informed about the potential benefits of the research, such as its potential to improve teaching practices and enhance student academic performance. All personal data was securely stored and treated as confidential to ensure privacy. Only aggregated data will be reported, ensuring anonymity, and participants can review their data to confirm accuracy. Participant selection was based on the study's requirements to ensure fair representation. All participants have equal access to any benefits of the research, and the study design avoided any bias in data collection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Teaching Quality

Instructional Methods

Table 1. Teaching Quality in Instructional methods

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher uses a variety of teaching methods to address different learning styles.	3.82	Strongly Agree
2. The lessons are well-structured and easy to follow.	3.68	Strongly Agree
3. The instruction encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	3.58	Strongly Agree
4. Real-life examples are integrated to enhance understanding.	3.64	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher provides regular formative feedback to improve student learning.	3.70	Strongly Agree
6. The teacher use ICT in delivery of lesson.	3.66	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.68	Strongly Agree

Based on the given ratings, the respondents strongly agree that the instructional methods used by the teachers are effective and well-designed to support diverse learning needs. The teachers employ various teaching methods, incorporate real-life examples, and provide regular formative feedback, which create a positive and engaging learning environment. This is reflected in the overall mean rating of 3.68, which falls within the "Strongly Agree" descriptive equivalent. All six indicators were rated highly, indicating that respondents perceived their teachers

as consistently effective in planning and delivering instruction. Item 1 received the highest rating of 3.82, which reflects strong appreciation for the use of varied teaching methods. Meanwhile, items 2 to 6 also fall under *Strongly Agree*, with item 3 (3.58) rated slightly lower, suggesting a slight gap in fostering critical thinking but still perceived positively.

Teacher-student interaction

Table 2. Teaching Quality in Teacher-student interaction

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher encourages students to actively participate in discussions and ask questions.	3.76	Strongly Agree
2. The teacher provides constructive feedback that helps improve my performance.	3.68	Strongly Agree
3. The teacher is approachable and makes me feel comfortable asking for help.	3.84	Strongly Agree
4. The teacher fosters a respectful and inclusive classroom environment.	3.82	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher is accessible outside class for additional help.	3.68	Strongly Agree
6 The teacher asks Low Order Thinking Skills (LOTS).	3.16	Agree
7. The teacher ask Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS).	3.44	Agree
Overall Mean	3.63	Strongly Agree

Based on the ratings provided, the respondents perceive teacher-student interactions as highly positive, noting that teachers are approachable, encourage participation, and foster a respectful and inclusive classroom atmosphere. While most items received strong agreement, the slightly lower ratings on higher-order thinking skills indicate room for growth in challenging students intellectually. The overall mean rating of 3.63 confirms a strong agreement with the quality of teacher-student interactions. Items 3 and 4 stood out with the highest ratings of 3.84 and 3.82, indicating that students feel their teachers are approachable and promote a respectful, inclusive environment. Items 1, 2, and 5, all scoring 3.68 or higher, suggest that students recognize teachers' consistent encouragement and support during and outside class sessions. However, items 6 (3.16) and 7 (3.44) showed lower ratings, shifting the interpretation from *Strongly Agree* to *Agree*. This implies that while interaction and support are strong, the intentional use of questioning techniques that promote low- and high-order thinking may be less emphasized.

Pedagogical competence

Table 3. Teaching Quality in Pedagogical Competence

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher demonstrates a strong understanding of the subject matter.	3.78	Strongly Agree
2. The teacher effectively uses technology to support learning.	3.68	Strongly Agree
3. Clear learning objectives are provided at the start of each lesson.	3.78	Strongly Agree
4. The teacher adapts their approach based on student progress.	3.80	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher maintains high standards of professionalism in the classroom.	3.74	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.76	Strongly Agree

Based on the responses, it is evident that the respondents strongly believe that their teachers possess strong pedagogical competence. Teachers demonstrate solid subject knowledge, adapt their approaches based on student progress, and maintain professionalism, all of which contribute to effective learning. The overall mean rating of 3.76, categorized as "Strongly Agree," supports this positive perception of pedagogical competence. This suggests that students perceive their teachers as highly competent in delivering content and managing the classroom. Items 1 and 3 both scored 3.78, reflecting the learners' confidence in their teachers' mastery of the subject and clarity in setting learning objectives. Item 4, with the highest rating of 3.80, highlights that students recognize their teachers' ability to adjust teaching approaches based on their progress. The ratings for items 2

(3.68) and 5 (3.74) also fall within the *Strongly Agree* range, indicating that the use of technology in instruction and professional behavior in class are both seen as strengths.

Level of Student Engagement

Cognitive Engagement

Table 4. Student Engagement in Cognitive

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. When I study, I try to understand the material better by relating it to things I already know.	3.88	Strongly Agree
2. When I study, I try to connect what I am learning with my own experiences.	3.54	Strongly Agree
3. When learning things for school, I often try to associate them with what I learned in other classes about the same or similar things.	3.44	Agree
4. I try to think through topics and decide what I'm supposed to learn from them, rather than studying topics by just reading them over.	3.48	Agree
5. When studying, I try to combine different pieces of information from course material in new ways.	3.56	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.58	Strongly Agree

Based on the given ratings, students generally show strong cognitive engagement by actively relating new knowledge to prior experiences and integrating information from various sources. While most indicators received strong agreement, some aspects, such as associating learning with other classes, showed slightly lower but positive agreement. The overall mean rating of 3.58 indicates a strong level of cognitive engagement among learners. This suggests that students actively use higher-level thinking skills and make meaningful connections during their learning. Item 1 received the highest rating of 3.88, showing that students often relate new knowledge to prior understanding. Similarly, items 2 and 5, rated above 3.50, indicate that learners regularly connect lessons to personal experiences and creatively synthesize information. Items 3 and 4, rated at 3.44 and 3.48, fall under *Agree*, which still signifies solid cognitive engagement but with slightly less intensity. These responses suggest that while students try to associate lessons across subjects and think critically, there's still room to strengthen these habits.

Affective Engagement

Table 5. Student Engagement in Affective

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I am very interested in learning.	3.86	Strongly Agree
2. I like what I am learning in school.	3.92	Strongly Agree
3. I enjoy learning new things in class.	3.82	Strongly Agree
4. I think learning is boring.	1.02	Strongly Disagree
5. Most mornings, I look forward to going to school.	3.58	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.24	Agree

Based on the ratings, students exhibit a strong positive attitude toward learning, expressing high interest, enjoyment, and motivation to attend school regularly. The very low score on the item regarding boredom strongly supports this enthusiasm for learning. The overall mean rating for affective engagement confirms that students are emotionally invested in their educational experience. Item 2 scored the highest at 3.92, followed by items 1 and 3, each close to or above 3.80, indicating that students enjoy learning and find it personally satisfying. Item 5, with a rating of 3.58, confirms students' eagerness to attend school regularly. Item 4, however, stands out with a very low rating of 1.02 (*Strongly Disagree*), clearly showing that students do not perceive learning as boring. This further strengthens the credibility of the other high ratings, validating learners' genuine interest and enthusiasm.

Psychomotor Engagement

Table 6. Student Engagement in Psychomotor

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
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1. I enjoy participating in physical activities that challenge my motor skills.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2. I feel confident in my ability to perform complex motor tasks.	3.42	Agree
3. I believe psychomotor activities enhance my overall well-being.	3.64	Strongly Agree
4. I actively seek out opportunities to engage in hands-on activities.	3.88	Strongly Agree
5. I am an active participant of school activities such as sports day and school picnics.	3.78	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.66	Strongly Agree

Based on the responses, students are actively involved and confident in engaging in physical and hands-on activities that challenge their motor skills. They also recognize the benefits of psychomotor activities for their overall well-being and frequently participate in school events. The overall mean of 3.66, corresponding to "Strongly Agree," reflects a high level of psychomotor engagement. Item 4 received the highest score of 3.88, indicating that students are highly inclined to engage in hands-on and movement-based activities. This is supported by item #5, which also scored highly at 3.78, showing students' active participation in school events that require physical involvement. These ratings reflect an eagerness to learn by doing. Although item 2 had a slightly lower score of 3.42 (*Agree*), it still points to a generally confident attitude toward motor skills. The rest of the items, such as 1 and 3, were rated above 3.60, highlighting students' appreciation for physical activities and their belief in the value of psychomotor development.

Level of Learning Experience Organization and Structure

Table 7. Learning Experience for Organization and Structure

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. It was clear to me what I was supposed to learn in the subjects.	3.40	Agree
2. The topics seemed to follow each other in a way that made sense to me.	3.16	Agree
3. We were given a good deal of choice over how we went about learning.	3.60	Strongly Agree
4. The subject was well organized and ran smoothly.	3.28	Agree
5. What we were taught seemed to match what we were supposed to learn.	3.78	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.44	Agree

Based on the ratings provided, the respondents generally agree that the organization and structure of their learning experiences are coherent and well-planned. The topics follow a logical sequence, and students appreciate having some choices in their learning methods. However, a few indicators fall slightly lower within the agreement range, indicating minor areas for improvement. The overall mean rating of 3.44 signifies an agreeable but not yet strong satisfaction with the organization and structure of the subjects. Item 5 had the highest rating of 3.78, indicating students perceived a strong alignment between the instruction they received and the intended learning outcomes. Item 3 also stood out with a *Strongly Agree* rating of 3.60, showing that students felt they had autonomy in their learning methods. However, items 2 and 4 scored more moderately at 3.16 and 3.28, suggesting that while the flow of topics and course structure was acceptable, there's room for improvement in making content progression smoother and more logical.

Teaching and Learning

Table 8. Learning Experience for Teaching and Learning

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The handouts and other materials we were given helped me to understand the lessons.	3.32	Agree
2. On my subjects, I was prompted to think about how well I was learning and how I might improve.	3.34	Agree
3. I could see the relevance of most of what we were taught in the subject.	3.32	Agree

4. The teaching encouraged me to rethink my understanding of some aspects of the subject.	3.50	Strongly Agree
5. Plenty of examples and illustrations were given to help us to grasp things better.	3.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.40	Agree

Based on the responses, students agree that teaching and learning processes are effective, with materials and examples helping them understand lessons better. The encouragement to reflect on their learning and rethink understanding is also positively noted. The overall mean rating of 3.40 suggests general agreement, indicating satisfactory teaching and learning experiences with potential for enhancement. Item 5, with a mean of 3.54, and item 4, at 3.50, were both *Strongly Agree*, implying that examples and thought-provoking instruction helped deepen their understanding. On the other hand, items 1, 2, and 3 scored around 3.32–3.34, showing that while learning materials and self-reflection were present, they were not consistently impactful across the board.

Students and Teachers

Table 9. Learning Experience for Students and Teachers

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Students supported each other and tried to give help when it was needed.	3.70	Strongly Agree
2. I found most of what I learned in the subject really interesting.	3.34	Agree
3. Talking with other students helped me to develop my understanding.	3.76	Strongly Agree
4. Students' views were valued in this course unit	3.48	Agree
5. I found I could generally work comfortably with other students on this unit.	3.38	Agree
OVERALL	3.53	Strongly Agree

Based on the given ratings, the respondents strongly agree that student support and peer collaboration play an important role in their learning experience. Interaction with peers is valued and contributes to deeper understanding, though some indicators reflect moderate agreement. The overall mean rating of 3.53 indicates a generally positive perception of the relationship between students and teachers within the learning environment. Item 3 had the highest score of 3.76, suggesting that peer discussions significantly improved understanding. Similarly, item 1 also received a high score of 3.70, reflecting strong student support within the learning community. Items 2, 4, and 5, with ratings from 3.34 to 3.48, received *Agree* interpretations. These show that while students appreciated having their views heard and could work comfortably with peers, there is still a slight gap in maximizing engagement and collaboration.

Assessments and Other Set Works

Table 10. Learning Experience for Assessments and Other Set Works

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
1. It was clear to me what was expected in the assessed work for the subjects.	3.34	Agree
2. The feedback given on my work helped me to improve my ways of learning and studying.	3.28	Agree
3. Doing the set work helped me to think about how evidence is used in this subject.	3.62	Strongly Agree
4. The set work helped me to make connections to my existing knowledge or experience.	3.68	Strongly Agree
5. The feedback given on my set work helped to clarify things I had not fully understood.	3.40	Agree
OVERALL	3.46	Agree

Based on the ratings provided, students agree that assessments and set work are clear and constructive, aiding their learning and helping them connect new knowledge with existing understanding. Feedback is perceived as helpful, although some aspects could be improved. The overall mean rating of 3.46 reflects an agreeable level of

satisfaction with assessment practices and related tasks. Item 4 scored highest at 3.68, followed by item 3 at 3.62, both under *Strongly Agree*, suggesting that the set works helped students connect lessons to their prior knowledge and understand evidence-based learning. Items 1, 2, and 5, with ratings ranging from 3.28 to 3.40, fell under *Agree*, indicating moderate effectiveness of assessment instructions and feedback. While feedback helped improve learning and clarify confusion, students might benefit from more targeted or detailed input.

Significant relationship between teaching quality and the level of student engagement of learners.

Table 11. Teaching Quality and Student Engagement

Pearson Correlations		
		Teaching Quality
Student Engagement	Pearson's r	0.209
	p-value	0.146

Table 11 presents the correlation between teaching quality and student engagement. The Pearson's r value is 0.209, which indicates a low positive correlation. However, the p-value of 0.146 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the relationship is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating no significant relationship between teaching quality and student engagement is accepted. This result suggests that variations in teaching quality do not significantly influence the level of student engagement among the respondents in this study.

Significant relationship between teaching quality and the level of learning experience of learners

Table 12. Teaching Quality and Learning Experience

Pearson Correlations		
		Teaching Quality
Learning Experience	Pearson's r	0.287
	p-value	0.044

Table 13 shows the correlation between teaching quality and learning experience. The Pearson's r value is 0.287, which indicates a low negative correlation, and the p-value is 0.044, less than the 0.05 significance level. This means the correlation is statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teaching Quality in Terms of Instructional Methods, Teacher-Student Interaction, and Pedagogical Competence. The findings revealed that the respondents rated the level of teaching quality as “Strongly Agree” across all indicators of instructional methods, teacher-student interaction, and pedagogical competence. This indicates that teachers effectively used varied strategies, maintained respectful classroom interactions, and demonstrated high levels of content mastery and instructional adaptability. According to Hattie (2009), teacher effectiveness—especially in the domains of feedback, classroom climate, and instructional clarity—significantly influences student learning outcomes. The consistently high ratings show that learners perceive their teachers as well-prepared and responsive to their academic needs. This aligns with findings by Huang (2024), who emphasized teaching quality's direct and indirect effects on student academic performance, highlighting the importance of pedagogical skills in enhancing learning outcomes. Similarly, Reyes and Bautista (2023) reported that when teachers exhibit instructional clarity, feedback sensitivity, and relational support, learners tend to exhibit greater academic involvement and confidence.

Student Engagement in Terms of Cognitive, Affective, and Psychomotor Engagement. The results demonstrated high student engagement, with “Strongly Agree” ratings particularly prominent in affective and psychomotor domains. Learners reported enthusiasm for learning, enjoyment in participating in classroom and extracurricular activities, and the ability to connect learning materials to prior knowledge and experience. This supports the findings of Fredricks, Blumenfeld, and Paris (2004), who emphasized that student engagement is a

multidimensional construct encompassing behavioral, emotional, and cognitive components that foster academic success. The lower yet still high ratings in the cognitive domain suggest a need for sustained strategies that develop critical and reflective thinking. This is consistent with the work of Li and Xue (2025), who found that positive teacher behaviors and supportive relationships significantly enhance student engagement by fulfilling psychological needs such as autonomy and relatedness.

Learning Experience in Terms of Organization and Structure, Teaching and Learning, Students and Teachers, and Assessments. The respondents expressed generally positive learning experiences, with most indicators falling under the “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” categories. This reflects a structured and student-centered approach to instruction. However, areas like "organization and structure" and "teaching and learning" showed slightly lower mean scores, suggesting opportunities to enhance lesson progression and provide clear learning expectations. Biggs (2011) asserts that meaningful learning occurs when students clearly understand learning objectives and how assessments align with them. The results imply that while the environment is conducive to learning, improvements in clarity, consistency, and student autonomy could further enrich the experience. Jowett et al. (2023) support this, noting that the quality of teacher-student relationships is a barometer for teaching and learning effectiveness, influencing student emotions and outcomes.

Significant Relationship Between Teaching Quality and Student Engagement. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.209$, $p = 0.146$) revealed a low but positive correlation between teaching quality and student engagement. However, the relationship is not statistically significant since the p-value is greater than 0.05. Thus, the decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This implies that while good teaching practices may positively influence student engagement, other factors such as personal motivation, peer relationships, or home environment may play a more prominent role. This finding contrasts with previous studies, such as Huang (2024), which identified student engagement as a mediator between teaching quality and academic performance, indicating that other factors may influence engagement levels.

Significant Relationship Between Teaching Quality and Learning Experience. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = -0.287$, $p = 0.044$) indicated a low but statistically significant negative correlation between teaching quality and learning experience. This surprising inverse relationship suggests that as perceived teaching quality increases, learners' perceptions of their learning experience slightly decrease. While the strength of this relationship is weak, the result may indicate a misalignment between teaching strategies and students' preferences or learning styles. This unexpected finding may reflect a misalignment between teaching methods, student expectations, and learning preferences. Li et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of aligning teaching practices with student needs to enhance learning experiences. There is no significant relationship between teaching quality and student engagement. There is a significant relationship between teaching quality and learning experience. The study reveals that students perceive teaching quality positively, as well as their engagement and learning experience. However, the complex nature of learning outcomes is highlighted by the absence of a significant correlation between teaching quality and student engagement, and the unexpected inverse relationship with learning experience. These results suggest that improving educational outcomes requires excellent teaching practices and better alignment between pedagogy, student perception, and learning design.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study sought to investigate the influence of teaching quality on learners' engagement and learning experience among elementary pupils. The findings revealed that while teachers demonstrate a high level of pedagogical competence and utilize appropriate instructional methods and teacher-student interactions, this perceived teaching quality does not significantly influence student engagement. This outcome challenges commonly held assumptions and suggests that engagement is a complex construct that may be influenced more by students' internal motivation, personal interests, peer relationships, and the learning environment than by teaching quality alone. Furthermore, discovering a significant negative correlation between teaching quality and learning experience is revealing and concerning. It may indicate that even when teaching is technically well-delivered, it may not always align with students' actual learning needs, styles, or preferences. This mismatch could stem from overly rigid teaching structures, a lack of differentiated instruction, or minimal student involvement in shaping the learning process. These insights underscore the importance of delivering quality instruction and ensuring that teaching strategies are flexible, inclusive, and centered on the learner's voice. Quality teaching alone does not automatically translate to high student engagement or positive learning experiences. The study suggests a need to shift toward a learner-centered approach, where teaching quality is contextualized, and student needs, feedback, and participation are integrated into instructional design. A more holistic view of quality teaching

should include emotional connection, relevance to students' lives, and the ability to spark curiosity and motivation.

1. Teachers and administrators should implement a structured and recurring system for gathering student feedback regarding their learning experiences, engagement, and perceptions of instructional quality. This can be done through surveys, reflection journals, or student-teacher consultations. By actively involving learners in evaluating the teaching process, educators can make timely adjustments that reflect students' real-time learning needs and concerns, ultimately improving alignment between teaching practices and learner expectations.

2. Professional development programs for teachers should emphasize the importance of cultivating strong, empathetic teacher-student relationships. Regular check-ins, personalized feedback, and creating a safe, inclusive classroom climate can increase emotional security and trust, vital precursors to engagement and deeper learning. When students feel respected and understood, they are more likely to participate actively and feel positively about their educational journey.

3. Teachers must be trained in differentiated instruction to address the observed disconnect between teaching quality and student learning experiences. This involves modifying content, processes, or products based on students' learning styles, interests, and readiness levels. Providing learners with voice and choice — such as selecting projects, pacing their tasks, or collaborating in ways that suit them — empowers students and makes learning more meaningful and engaging.

4. Educators should review existing assessment strategies to ensure they are evaluative and developmental. Assessments should include opportunities for students to reflect on their performance and apply feedback to improve future work. Providing clear rubrics, exemplars, and descriptive feedback can bridge gaps in understanding and promote metacognitive skills. Moreover, allowing revisions and follow-up tasks can increase students' ownership of their learning.

5. Schools should create spaces where teachers can engage in collaborative planning, peer observations, and reflective dialogue about their teaching practices and student outcomes. Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) can facilitate ongoing learning, support innovation in pedagogy, and ensure consistency in addressing diverse student needs. Teachers learning from each other — through shared best practices and peer support — can refine strategies that better connect quality teaching with authentic student engagement and experiences.

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